

Analysis of Urban Expansion in Oyi Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Urban expansion is often characterized by the outward growth of cities into suburban areas, posed significant challenges to agricultural land preservation and food security. This study examined the extent of urban expansion in Oyi Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria, using satellite imagery and GIS techniques. Analysis of land use change over a 35-year period revealed a notable increase in built-up areas accompanied by a decline in agricultural land, vegetation, and water bodies. Similar trends were observed in both Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike communities, highlighting the urgent need for sustainable land management policies and practices. Recommendations made based on findings of the study include the implementation of comprehensive land use planning frameworks, conservation measures, and community engagement initiatives to mitigate the adverse impacts of urban expansion on ecosystems and human livelihoods.

Keywords: Urban expansion, Agricultural land, Land use change, Satellite imagery

1. Introduction

Urban expansion is the growth of urban areas into the city fringes. Otherwise referred to as urban sprawl, urban expansion can also be seen as the outward growth of the city into the suburbs (Unah, 2021). Urban expansion is largely associated with the growth in human population and expansion of building mass. This is due to the fact that as population increases, the demand for infrastructure such as housing units, commercial venture/complexes and other developments become inevitable. Aniekwe and Igu (2019) opined that the expansion of urban areas is a feature of urban development pattern, which has emerged as a dominant mode of growth worldwide.

While urban expansion appears to be unavoidable due to increase in population growth and demand for housing, agricultural lands tends to be the most affected in the sprawling process. This is because the erection of physical developments in the suburbs through the urban expansion process leads to encroachment into farmlands, thereby decreasing available lands for agricultural development. It should be noted that lands in the suburbs are primarily preserved and are mostly used for agricultural purposes (Aniekwe and Igu, 2019). Unfortunately, as agricultural lands are being built on, food security becomes threatened since these lands are required to support agricultural productivity. Essentially, production of food is largely dependent on land availability considering that land is an indispensable and limited factor of production. Therefore, shortage of agricultural land translates to unavoidable insecurity in food production.

Globally, the upsurge in human population, which is largely tied to economic, social and physical changes is linked to rapid urbanization and industrialization. These factors give rise to intense pressure on agricultural resources, through uncontrolled encroachment into farmlands (Eliud, Lucy, Bernard & Samuel,

2019). However, urbanization and population growth are bound to increase in the next three decades, with not less than two third of the world population residing in urban centres by the year 2050 (Assem, Maria, August, & Carl-Johan, 2019). This is in accordance with World Bank (2000) forecast which suggests that there would be an unprecedented growth in global population with not less than seventy percent (70%) of the world population living in towns and cities (Drebold, 2017). The statistics show that most peri-urban areas will later become urban areas due to growth and city expansion and agricultural land is likely to experience decline.

In Nigeria, Anambra State and its major urban areas such as Awka, Nnewi and Onitsha have experienced increased urban population and the expansion of physical development within its environs. This has led to the sudden conversion of arable land, ecosystems and water bodies especially at the peripheries of the town into built up areas. The foregoing study seeks to analyse the extent of urban expansion in Oyi Local Government Area, Anambra State.

2. Literature Review

Etim and Atser (2023) characterized the land use of the Ikot Ekpene LGA into four classes of thick forest, cultivated farm land, built up area and water body. The result of image analysis showed that in 1980, thick forest was the dominant land use covering 45.98% of the study area, cultivated farm land took up 30.65% of the area, Built-up area and water body took up 20.35% and 3.02 % respectively. In the year 2000, cultivated farmland became the dominant land use class with an areal coverage of 56.333km² (44.19%), built up area was 45.346km² (35.57%), thick forest covered an area of 25.755km² (20.20%) and water body had an areal extent of 3.046km² (2.39%). However in the year 2020, the built up area was the dominant land use class covering 61.529km² (48.27%) of the study area, cultivated farmland covered 33.231km² (26.06%), thick forest had an areal extent of 30.158km² (23.66%) and water body had an areal extent of 2.562km² (2.01%). The built up area increased by 35.591km² at an annual change of 20.008%. The study established that urban development has greatly induced land use change in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area with a drastic increase in the built-up area while farmland, water bodies and forests experienced significant decrease, and thus, it was recommended that there is urgent need for environmental conservation and protection in the region.

Alfred *et al.* (2016) monitored the land use changing pattern with focus on the built –up areas in Suleja LGA, Niger State. The study showed that built-up areas increased from 650.60 hectares in 1980 to 3061; 13 hectares in 2015, an increase of 4637.49 hectares (39%). The study made use of Landsat Imagery of Suleja, data were presented in form of histograms, bar charts, figures, imageries and tables. Uhwache, Sawa and Jaiyeoba (2015) carried out a study on land use dynamics in Zaria between 1973 and 2009 . The findings indicated that Zaria is experiencing rapid expansion leading to a large chunk of the scrubland, farmlands and even part of the flood plains giving way to residential buildings with built-up areas increasing from 44.27 km² in 1973 to 130.25 km² in 2009, while Fadama lands decreased from 146.35km² in 1973 to 571.29 km² in 2009, plantation/forest decreased from 89.24 km² in 1973 to 63.36 km² in 2009, scrubland decreased from 1,765.72 km² in 1973 to 1,350.39km² in 2009 and water bodies from 38.16km² in 1973 to 4.20km² in 2009.

Ukor *et al* (2016) found out that within 2002 to 2013, the built areas in Ikeja increased by 319.64 hectares (10.66%) and shrub land increased by 380.97 hectares (193.06%). This led to the decrease in vegetated lands by 50.28% (a loss of 701.22 hectares). Fred (2019) studied the effects of land use changes on agriculture in Abak LGA, Akwa Ibom State. The results of the research showed that between 1986 and 2016, the forested land cover

decreased by 2312.82 hectares at a rate of 77 hectares a year and the disturbed forest decreased by 433.07 hectares at a rate of 14.43 hectares per year. Farmlands decreased by 40,992 hectares at the rate of 1366 hectares per year, while the built up areas increased by 3338.56 hectares at the rate of 111.29 hectares per year. It was noted that uncontrolled land use change was posing a great threat to agricultural practices in the area.

Etim, Attah and Okon (2023) assessed land use change in Itu LGA, Nigeria using Relative Shannon Entropy. The RSE was determined to be 0.6114, confirming that there was a considerable change in the study area's land use pattern between 1992 and 2022. The findings of the study revealed notable trends in land use change, including a decline in water bodies and wetlands, an increase in the built-up areas and cultivated lands, and a reduction in fallowed land. It was concluded that the unguided pattern of land use change being experienced in the area was unsustainable as it has serious implications on the environment.

3. Materials and Method

3.1 Study Area

The geographic location of the study area is Oyi Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. It is necessary to point out here that the study area is one of the 21 Local Government Areas of Anambra State. It is located between Latitudes 5° and 7° North and Longitudes 6° and 7° East. The study area is located at the South-West of Awka the capital of Anambra State and on East of River Niger (Figures 1 and Figure 2). It occupies a land area of about 500sqKms which is predominantly grassland vegetation. Annually two distinct seasons are observed in the study area. They are the rainy season, which is normally from the period of April to October, and the dry season which is from the period of November to March annually. The area has a warm humid tropical climate, with an average rainfall of between 1520-2020mm per annum. Minimum and maximum temperatures range from 25°C to 30°C, (Ifeka, and Akinbobola, 2015). The climate of the area allows for favourable cultivation and extraction of agricultural and forest products such as oil palm, maize, rice, yam, cassava, and fishing activities. Oyi Local Government Area and its environs belong to the equatorial rain forest belt of West Africa and receives more than 80 in mm of rainfall annually, mostly during seven months of the rainy season

The five autonomous communities which make up Oyi LGA are Awkuzu, Nteje, Umunya, Ogbunike and Nkwelle-Ezunaka. The communities are known for their vast agricultural farming in both crop and livestock production. Being agrarian in nature, they are essentially agric-based and reputed as one of the food baskets of Anambra State. It has wide arable land and the crops grown include: rice, yam seeds, cassava, cocoyam, maize and vegetables. Domestic animals are goats, sheep and fowl. Due to the system of land ownership in the area, cultivation of crop is relatively in small land holdings by individual farmers who practice cropping often with fallow system (Nkamigbo, Nwoye, Makwudo & Gbughemobi, 2019).

Figure 1: Administrative Map of Anambra State Showing Oyi LGA

Source:Jorinno Survey Services & Assoc. Nig., (2022)

Figure 2: Map of Oyi LGA

Source: Jorinno Survey Services & Assoc. Nig., (2022)

3.2 Methods

Data were obtained using oral interviews and observations, Geographic Information System (GIS), Global Positioning System (GPS), linear measurements and estimations of lost agricultural lands and land use changes for the past 35 years was determined using change detection techniques and satellite images. Purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting the peri-urban areas in Oyi LGA. Therefore, Ogbunike and Nkwelle-Ezunaka were selected. The areas were chosen because of the high rate of physical development, urban expansion and the change in land uses which is evident in the presence of large built up areas. Data were basically collected and analysed using GIS technologies. Furthermore, the study utilized Landsat TM, 1986; Landsat ETM, 2006, Landsat 8, 2016 and Landsat 8, 2020 acquired online, through the website of global landcover facility (<http://glcf.umiacs.umd.edu>) on June 18, 2021. Image was stored in the hard drive of Laptop computer, EliteBook8440p. Handheld GPS (Garmin 76) was used to generate the coordinates of some selected ground control points in the study area which were used to georeference and resampling the acquired images, ArcGIS version10.5 software was used to import the satellite imageries to ENVI 5.1 for further processing. ENVI 5.1 was utilized for the development of land use/land cover classes and subsequently for change detection

analysis of the study area, while, Microsoft word and excel were used basically for the presentation of the research.

In the area data presentation and pre-processing, the images were loaded, imported and displayed in the ArcGIS version 10.5 environment. The images were processed using digital image processing techniques, such as image enhancement and filtering to improve the pictorial quality of the images. Subset operation was performed on the images to create the Area of Interest (AOI). Landsat TM and ETM 1986, 2006 and Landsat 2016, 2020 were resampled to cater for differences in their spatial resolutions using polynomial transformation and bicubic resampling method. Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out on LANDSAT MSS for effective image classification. The multispectral bands were reduced to 3 components of RGB so that the colour composite that will follow will make use of all the information in the bands.

Next is image classification, which is the process of sorting pixels into a finite number of individual classes, or categories of data, based on their data file values which may be described as multispectral classification. This involves the training of computer to recognize patterns in the remotely sensed image. A supervised method was utilized simply because it permits selection of pixels that represent patterns or land use features that is recognizable or identifiable with the use of other sources such as ground truth data and topographical maps.

4. Results and Discussions

The explanations and the implication of the image classification and comprehensive discussion of the results are as follows:

Land use/cover change in Nkwelle-Ezunaka

Built-up Area (BA): The rate of Built-up Area (BA) change between 1986 and 2006 is 07.75%, between 2006 and 2016 is 02.18%, and while from 2016 to 2022 is 10.88%. Because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature for say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was used to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 and 2022. The value is computed to be 20.81%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is 26.59% still indicating a positive proliferation.

Vegetation (VG): Vegetation (VG) change between 1986 and 2006 is 03.56%, between 2006 and 2016 is 19.44%, and while from 2016 to 2022 is -17.086%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature for say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was used to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 and 2022. The value is computed to be 05.91%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is 4.27% still designating a positive growth.

Water Bodies (WB): Water Bodies (WB) change between 1986 and 2006 -02.11%, between 2006 and 2016 is -20.72%, and while from 2016 to 2022 is -00.73%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature of say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was use to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 to 2022. The value is computed to be -22.97%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is -4.79% representing a negative upsurge.

Farm Land (FL): Farm Land (FL) change between 1986 and 2006 -09.19%, between 2006 and 2016 is -20.72%, and while from 2016 to 2022 is 06.94%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature of say 5yrs

temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was use to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 to 2022. The value is computed to be 0.35%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is -29.35% demonstrating a negative proliferation.

Figure 3: Profile of satellite image classification of Nkwelle Ezunaka

Figure 4. The visual illustration of the above explanations on the satellite image classification of Nkwelle-Ezunaka

Table 1: The difference in landuse and landcover of Nkwelle-Ezunaka from 1986 to 2020

NKWELLE CLASSES	DIFFERENCE IN LULC YEARS IN %				RATE OF CHANGE %	PROJ %
	2006-1986 (20yrs)	2016-2006 (10yrs)	2020-2016 (6yrs)	2020-1986 (34yrs)	2020-1986 (34yrs)	2030-2020 (10yrs)
BA	07.75	02.18	10.88	20.81	00.578	05.78
VG	03.56	19.44	-17.086	05.91	-00.164	-01.64
WB	-02.11	-00.91	-00.73	-03.75	-00.104	-01.04
FL	-09.19	-20.72	06.94	-22.97	-00.638	-06.38

Land use/Cover change in Ogbunike

Similarly, just like in the case of Nkwelle-Ezunaka, image classification was used for four different epochs of satellite imageries. The result is indicates peri-urban dynamism of Ogbunike community from 1986 to 2020.

Built-up Area (BA): The rate of Built-up Area (BA) change between 1986 and 2006 is 0.12%, between 2006 and 2016 is 0.84%, and while from 2016 to 2020 is 2.43%. Because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature of say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was used to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 and 2020. The value is computed to be 0.70%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is 32.131% still indicating a positive proliferation. This is confirmed by the increase in population and infrastructure development in this community.

Vegetation (VG): This class of land includes savannah, grassland, mixed forestland and plantations. Vegetation (VG) change between 1986 and 2006 is 0.73%, between 2006 and 2016 is -23.51%, and while from 2016 to 2020 is -13.65%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature of say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was use to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 to 2022. The value is computed to be -0.98%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is -36.406% still designating a negative growth. Though, the percentage of change varies over the years, signifying the degree of these anthropogenic activities across the years.

Water Bodies (WB): This class includes rivers, streams and lakes. Water Bodies (WB) change between 1986 and 2006 -00.72%, between 2006 and 2016 is 02.13%, and while from 2016 to 2020 is -03.80%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature of say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was use to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 to 2022. The value is computed to be -0.66%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is -03.05% representing a negative upsurge. The results also suggest the level of human activities such as sand mining, siltation, development on the fringes of banks and sometime reclamation for structural development. Worse still is the dumping of refuse bin into these bodies.

Farm Land (FL): This class includes cultivated lands. Farm Land (FL) change between 1986 and 2006 - 03.16%, between 2006 and 2016 is 12.94%, and while from 2016 to 2020 is 02.89%. Again, because the image Epoch is not uniform in nature say 5yrs temporal resolution or 10yrs temporal resolution, the overall change was use to obtain the value of the rate of change between 1986 to 2022. The value is computed to be 0.35%. Consequently, projection to 2032 is 16.19% demonstrating a positive proliferation. This change is more dynamic in urban showing urban encroachment (and thus clearly showing that the only available land is remaining in the rural fringe). The visual illustration of the above explanations on the satellite image classification of Ogbunike.

Figure 4: visual result of satellite image classification of Ogbunike

Table 2 :Landuse and Landcover Change Detection of Ogbunike between 1986 and 2020

OGBUNIKE CLASSES	DIFFERENCE IN LULC YEARS IN %				RATE OF CHANGE %	PROJ %
	2006-1986 (20yrs)	2016-2006 (10yrs)	2020-2016 (6yrs)	2020-1986 (36yrs)		
CLASSES LULC					2020-1986 (36yrs)	2032-2022 (10yrs)
BA	02.153	08.439	14.554	25.146	00.700	32.131
VG	01.733	-23.506	-13.649	-35.422	-00.984	-36.406
WB	-00.719	02.13	-03.799	-02.388	-00.066	-03.051
FL	-03.163	12.936	02.894	12.667	00.352	16.187

BA: Built-up areas, **VG:** Vegetation, **WB:** Water Bodies, **FL:** Farm Land

The extent to which urban expansion has diminished agricultural land between 1986 and 2020 was examined using the Landsat TM, 1986; Landsat ETM, 2006, Landsat 8, 2016 and Landsat 8, 2020. In Nkwelle-Ezunaka, it was observed that the built up areas increased from 5985900.000Sqm in 1986 to 7875900.500Sqm in 2006. By 2006, the total built up area was 8409600, while in 2020, the built up area had increased to 11070000Sqm. While the built up area was increasing, there was sharp decrease in the farm land, for instance, it was noted in the study that in 2006, total farm land in Nkwelle-Ezunaka was 11304000Sqm which decreased to 9043200Sqm in 2006. 2016, it was 3976200Sqm. The climax of the decrease was in 2020 when the farm lands only account for 5673600Sqm. The decrease in farm land and reverse increase in built up areas suggest withdrawal of land from agricultural to other land uses suggesting that food production is likely to decline correspondingly as land becomes scarce over the years. There is also withdrawal of land from vegetation and water bodies as noted in the study. The withdrawal of land from vegetation which show sharp decrease in the

availability of reserved areas suffice that the plant ecosystem is largely tampered with. These further explain that the environment is at risk of receiving several negative implications if efforts are not carried out to slow the tide of land withdrawal from the natural environment.

In Ogbunike, the case is not different. For instance, the study noted that in 1986, built up area accounted for a total of 7692601.7427sqm, while there was increase in 2006 to a total of 8143791.2316SqM becoming built up, while in 2016, the built up areas has increased up to 9913635.7149sqm depicting an increase from 36.686 percent in 1986 to 47.278 percent in 2016. The increase in the built up areas became heightened by 2020 with a total of 12,965,431.2858SqM becoming built up accounting for a sporadic increase of 61.832 percent. The increase appears sharp and intense yet showing retarding results on land availability for vegetation, farm land and water bodies all of which constrain agricultural expansion and development further resulting in food insecurity. Reasons that account for increase in the built up areas including population growth, poor land conservation approaches and accompanying absence of legislations targeted at land use changes. The continuous conversion of land from agriculture and food production is not without negative implications. For instance, food insecurity becomes inevitable in the mist of land shortage. Similar land conversions from other uses to build up areas were earlier observed in peri urban areas in the work of Etim and Atser (2023) and Omang (2022).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis of land use/cover change in Nkwelle-Ezunaka and Ogbunike reveals significant trends over the studied periods, reflecting both positive and negative implications for the environment and human settlements. In Nkwelle-Ezunaka, there is a notable increase in built-up areas, accompanied by a decline in farm land, vegetation, and water bodies. Similarly, Ogbunike experiences a surge in built-up areas, leading to a reduction in available land for vegetation, farming, and water bodies.

These findings underscore the pressing need for sustainable land management practices and policies to mitigate adverse effects on ecosystems and human livelihoods. It is imperative to implement measures aimed at conserving agricultural land, preserving natural habitats, and safeguarding water resources. Additionally, efforts should be directed towards enhancing urban planning strategies to accommodate population growth while minimizing encroachment on agricultural land and natural landscapes. Furthermore, addressing the underlying drivers of land use change, such as population growth, inadequate land conservation practices, and ineffective land use policies, is essential for fostering sustainable development and ensuring food security. Collaboration between stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, and environmental organizations, is crucial for formulating and implementing effective land use planning and management initiatives.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that comprehensive land use planning frameworks be established, incorporating environmental conservation objectives, socio-economic considerations, and community participation. Moreover, efforts to raise awareness and promote sustainable land use practices among stakeholders should be prioritized to foster a collective commitment to preserving the integrity of our landscapes and ensuring the well-being of present and future generations.

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Suggested Citation

- Ikedigwe, C., Ezeomodo, I. and Akanwa, A. (2024). Analysis of Urban Expansion in Oyi Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Development, Sustainability and Environmental Management* 4 (2) 14-25.

Appendix

Classified Landuse and Landcover of Nkwelle-Ezunaka

Classified Landuse and Landcover of Ogbunike Community